

Chapter 19

Combining Clustering and Predictive Algorithms for Real Estate Market Trends – Literature Review

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Combining Clustering and Predictive Algorithms for Real Estate Market Trends – Literature Review

Sara Oliveira Pinto^{1,*}, Nuno Rafael Reis Teixeira Fidalgo¹, Halima Moukrime², Tiago Alexandre Pais Dias¹, Rafaela Oliveira Carvalho¹, Fernanda Brito Correia¹

¹ Polytechnic University of Coimbra, Rua da Misericórdia, Lagar dos Cortiços, S. Martinho do Bispo, 3045-093, Coimbra, Portugal

² Università di Reggio Emilia e Modena, Via P.Vivarelli 10, 42125 Modena MO, Italy,

*Corresponding author

a2021129757@isec.pt

Abstract

The real estate market is a complex and dynamic sector influenced by various economic, social, and environmental factors. Clustering and predictive modeling have emerged as powerful tools for analyzing market trends, estimating property values, and segmenting real estate assets. This paper presents a literature review on the application of predictive models integrated with clustering algorithms within the field of Machine Learning. This combined approach has demonstrated improved prediction accuracy, particularly when using Regression and Decision Tree-Based models. However, clustering techniques alone have not shown a significant impact on enhancing property categorization. The review highlights the advantages of combining clustering techniques with predictive methods for precise market prediction and segmentation, demonstrating their effectiveness through case studies and comparative analyses. Nevertheless, some critical issues remain, especially those related to data complexity. All these findings contribute to the advancement of data-driven strategies in real estate market analysis, supporting informed decision-making for investors, policymakers, and real estate professionals.

Keywords: real estate price prediction; predictive modeling; Clustering; Machine Learning; trend analysis

1 Introduction

The real estate market plays a key role in economic stability, with trends shaped by factors such as economic conditions, population growth, interest rates, and policy changes. Traditional analytical methods often struggle to handle the market's complexity. Recently, data analytics, including Machine Learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool for predicting prices, identifying trends, and segmenting markets [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Predictive modeling enables accurate property valuation, while clustering groups similar properties for clearer market segmentation [6, 7, 8, 9]. This paper explores the combined use of these techniques to enhance real estate analysis, offering practical insights for investors, developers, policymakers, and homebuyers [3, 8, 10].

Four Research Questions (RQs) were formulated to guide the exploration of ML techniques in the context of clustering and predictive modeling within the real estate market. These RQs aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of various ML methods on model performance, as well as the challenges faced in optimizing and selecting appropriate algorithms. The list of the RQs is in Table 1, where N is RQ number.

Overall, this work does an analysis of the existing literature on clustering techniques and predictive modeling applied to the real estate market. After this introduction, where the RQs are presented, the methodology used to identify and select the relevant studies are described. Then, the results that emerged from the analysis are presented followed by the reflections derived from these results offering answers to the RQs highlighting both the main challenges and possible strategies to address them. Finally, the study concludes with a summary of its main contributions, acknowledges its limitations, and proposes directions for future research.

Table 1: List of Research Questions

N	RQ	Description
RQ1	How do different ML approaches impact the efficiency of clustering and predictive models?	To examine how different ML techniques influence prediction accuracy and clustering efficiency.
RQ2	How do supervised and unsupervised ML techniques complement each other in clustering and predictive modeling?	To explore how supervised and unsupervised learning combine to improve clustering and prediction.
RQ3	How can ML algorithms be tailored to enhance both clustering and predictive performance?	To examine the optimization of ML algorithms for clustering and prediction via tuning, feature selection, and hybrid methods.
RQ4	What are the key challenges in selecting and optimizing ML algorithms for clustering and prediction?	To address clustering and prediction methods for real estate, with focus on overfitting, scalability, and interpretability.

2 Methodology

To conduct this review, an analysis of the literature was carried out. The literature review followed a stage process inspired by the methodology proposed by Kitchenham [11]. The search strategy begins by selecting Google Scholar to track scientific papers that address the intersection of clustering, prediction, and the real estate market. The central theme of this review focuses on research articles that explore "Clustering," "Predicting," "Real Estate Market," "Prices," and "machine learning". The search string used to retrieve articles from Google Scholar was: “Clustering AND Predicting AND ‘Real Estate Market’ AND Prices AND ‘machine learning’”.

To ensure the relevance of the articles, we applied two search preconditions: the articles must be written in English and published since 2020. These criteria help to narrow the search to the most recent and pertinent studies in the field, focusing on modern approaches to clustering and prediction models using ML applied to real estate pricing. The inclusion and exclusion criteria for this review are explained in Table 2.

Table 2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criterium	Exclusion criterium
Discuss or apply ML algorithms like K-Means, DBSCAN, Random Forest, Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Neural Networks, to predict or cluster real estate price data.	Address other areas of predicting with ML or clustering that do not involve the real estate market.

These inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to narrow the selection of relevant studies during the review process, ensuring that only articles that directly contribute to the intersection of ML techniques and real estate price prediction or clustering were considered.

The identification phase began with a Google Scholar search, using the mentioned search string, which initially retrieved 1330 articles. Applying the exclusion criteria in the analysis of the titles, 1295 articles were excluded and, when applying the exclusion criteria in the analysis of the abstracts, 10 articles remained.

During the eligibility phase, these 10 articles were fully analyzed to ensure they met the inclusion criteria, focusing on the application of ML algorithms for clustering and predictive modeling in the real estate market. Ultimately, these 10 articles were confirmed as the final set for review and included in the study, Figure 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

3 Results

Figure 2 shows the trend of publications over 5 years. Out of the 10 selected articles, the highest number were published in 2024.

The studies identified used different datasets and arrived at varied conclusions, reflecting the diversity of approaches and contexts within the real estate domain. Table 3 summarizes the datasets used in each study.

Figure 2: Year-wise distribution of publications selected

Table 3: Datasets from selected articles

Article	Datasets
[1]	Compiled using data obtained from various internet real estate sites
[2]	Web scraping from Kadıköy, Istanbul; Kaggle dataset: The Ames Housing"
[3]	Property data in the city of Bangalore, India
[4]	Datasets include UCI's Boston Housing, Zillow (USA), Taiwan Real Estate Transactions, Kaggle, Magicbricks, 99 acres, government sources, REPD-3000 (textual/visual data), geospatial/satellite images, and real data from Taichung, Taiwan (2016–2019).
[5]	Dataset provided by the consulting firm Empirica ag (2016-2019)
[6]	Sourced from the Ministry of the Interior, Taiwan

Article	Datasets
[7]	Data analyzed comes from user interactions on an online real estate portal
[8]	No information
[9]	Historical transaction data from the Swedish market from the cadastral and land registration authority.
[10]	The data used was prepared with 121 criteria, incorporating approximately 200,000 real estate values.

The review revealed a wide range of predictive algorithms used in real estate trend analysis. Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) was the most frequent (60%), followed by Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) (50%), Random Forest, RIDGE Regression (40%), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), XGBoost, and LightGBM (30% each). Boosting methods like Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost), appeared in 20% of studies. Regularization techniques (Bayesian Ridge Regression, RANSAC Regression, ElasticNet) were also applied in 10–20% of cases. Specialized models such as Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS), Least Squares Support Vector Regression (LSSVR), Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, SVM, and Genetic Algorithms (GA) were used in 10–20% of the articles. Neural network variants like Back-propagation Neural Network (BPNN) and General Regression Neural Network (GRNN) appeared in 20%, and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) in 10%. Hybrid/ensemble models such as Particle Swarm Optimization-Bagging-Artificial Neural Networks (PSO-Bagging-ANNs) and GSNE were found in 10% of the studies. Tree-based models like Classification and Regression Tree (CART) were applied in 20%, showing good interpretability. Figure 3 presents an overview of the predictive models used in the selected articles. These predictive models were categorized into Regression Models, Decision Trees, Tree-Based Models, Neural Networks, Optimization and Hybrid methods and Ensemble Models emphasizing the diversity of approaches applied to real estate price prediction and classification tasks.

Figure 3: Taxonomy of predictive models

Table 4 to Table 8, Figure 4 and Table 9 show the studies that used the mentioned algorithms, ordered by decreasing number of papers that use them, each table for each of the categories.

Clustering techniques used by the studies were diverse. K-Means was the most used (20%), followed by Balanced Iterative Reducing and Clustering using Hierarchies (BIRCH), Gaussian Mixture, Hierarchical Clustering, Spatially Constrained Multivariate Clustering Analysis (SCMCA), Cluster and Outlier Analysis, Prototype-Based Models, and Data Mining (10% each).

Table 4: Regression Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
MLR	[1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7]
LASSO	[1, 2, 4, 5, 8]
SVR	[2, 4, 5, 10]
RIDGE Regression	[1, 2, 4, 5]
ElasticNet	[1, 4]
LSSVR	[6]
MARS	[1]
Bayesian Ridge Regression	[5]
RANSAC Regression	[5]

Table 5: Decision Tree Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
Decision Trees	[2, 3, 4]
Classification and Regression Trees	[6]

Table 6: Tree-Based Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
Random Forest	[1, 2, 4, 10]
XGBoost	[1, 2, 4]
LightGBM	[1, 4, 5]
AdaBoost	[1, 2]
CatBoost	[1]

Table 7: Classification Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
K-Nearest Neighbors	[1, 2, 4]
Naive Bayes	[4, 10]
Logistic Regression	[4]
SVM	[5]

Table 8: Neural Network Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
ANN	[1, 4, 7]
BPNN	[4, 6]
GRNN	[4, 6]

Figure 4: Optimization and Hybrid Models applied by selected articles

Table 9: Ensemble Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
Gradient Boosting	[4]

Figure 5 shows the taxonomy of the clustering algorithms used in the selected articles. They were categorized as Partition-Based Models, Hierarchical Models, Prototype-Based Models and Spatial Models.

Table 10 to Table 13 show the studies that used the mentioned algorithms, ordered by decreasing number of papers that use them, each table for each of the categories.

Evaluating the performance of predictive models and clustering algorithms in the real estate market is essential to ensure the accuracy and effectiveness of the predictions and groupings generated. Next, are presented the main metrics used to evaluate prediction and clustering models applied to trend analysis in the real estate market, according to the studies analyzed.

- Regression Models: Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) was the most used metric (50%), followed by Mean Absolute Error (MAE) (40%), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Normalized Mean Absolute Error (NMAE) (30%), Coefficient of Determination (COD), Percentage Root-mean-square Difference (PRD), Mean Squared Error (MSE) and R-squared (R^2) (20%), and Adjusted R^2 , Root Mean Squared Logarithmic Error (RMSLE), Cross-validation (10%).
- Classification Models: Accuracy was the most frequent (30%), while True Positive Rate (TPR), True Negative Rate (TNR), Precision, Recall, F1-measure, and Support were used in 10% of the studies.

Figure 5: Taxonomy of clustering models

Table 10: Partition-Based Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
K-Means	[1, 2]
BIRCH	[1]
Gaussian	[1]

Table 11: Hierarchical Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
Hierarchical Clustering	[1]

Table 12: Prototype-Based Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
Prototype-Based Learning	[8]
KNN with Nystroem method	[5]

Table 13: Spatial Analysis Models applied by selected articles

Algorithm	Papers
SCMCA	[9]
Cluster and Outlier Analysis	[9]

Table 14 presents the main conclusions drawn by each study.

Table 14: Conclusions from selected articles

Article	Conclusions
[1]	Best weak model: Ridge (MAPE 4.9%, MAE 30,756 TL); best meta-model: ANN (MAPE 3.2%, MAE 19,931 TL), outperforming all individual models.
[2]	The study concluded that the hybrid model (Linear Regression (LR), clustering analysis, KNN and Support Vector Regression (SVR)) is effective in predicting real estate prices, offering higher accuracy compared to traditional methods.
[3]	The application of ML algorithms (LR and Decision Tree) can improve accuracy in predicting property prices, facilitating more informed decisions in the property market.
[4]	ML was used in 61.5% of studies; Deep Learning, though promising, was underused (7.7%); Hybrid models (30.8%) offered better accuracy; ensemble methods like Random Forest, XGBoost, and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) were most effective; key factors included geographical, structural, and macroeconomic influences.
[5]	Combining clustering techniques with predictive algorithms improved the analysis of real estate market trends, although accuracy depends on the quality and detail of the data available.
[6]	LSSVR with genetic tuning and feature selection effectively predicts real estate prices; ML models are reliable for prediction using transaction data; feature selection boosts accuracy; Deep learning and unstructured data hold future potential.
[7]	The study demonstrated that personalization based on interactions with digital maps improved property recommendations and can help users make more informed decisions about purchasing and investing in real estate.
[8]	The prototype-based learning model can capture non-linear relationships and offers a degree of explainability by summarizing real estate datasets into a few representative “prototypes”.
[9]	The proposed methodology, which combines dataset optimization, cluster analysis and multiple regression, significantly improved the performance of massive property evaluation. Using geographic value clusters resulted in more accurate predictions than applying the model across the entire study area.

- [10] K-Means was the top clustering model. For prediction, Naive Bayes, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) were evaluated, with Naive Bayes achieving 99.6% accuracy and Random Forest and SVM both reaching 99.9%.

5 Discussion

The choice of appropriate metrics to evaluate predictive models and clustering algorithms depends on the purpose of the analysis and the characteristics of the data. In the context of the real estate market, metrics such as RMSE, R^2 and PRD are essential for measuring the quality of predictions, while the Silhouette Score and Davies-Bouldin Index are useful for assessing the efficiency of market segmentation. In addition, for classification models, metrics such as accuracy and precision make it possible to measure the effectiveness of property categorization. The correct application of these metrics allows for a more robust and well-founded analysis, contributing to better strategic decisions in the real estate sector.

After conducting a thorough analysis of the studies, the RQs defined at the beginning of this work are answered.

RQ1: How do different ML approaches impact the efficiency of clustering and predictive models? Different models impact the efficiency of clustering and predictive algorithms depending on data characteristics and analysis objectives. For example, Regression Models like MLR helped estimate relationships between variables in various contexts [1]. Tree-based models such as Random Forest and XGBoost were widely used due to their ability to handle large volumes of data and improve prediction accuracy: Random Forest, a powerful ensemble method, aggregates multiple decision trees to enhance predictive accuracy [3]. In clustering, K-Means stood out for its efficiency in grouping data, appearing in 20% of the articles due to its effectiveness in partitioning data into distinct groups.

RQ2: How do supervised and unsupervised ML techniques complement each other in clustering and predictive modeling? Supervised and unsupervised techniques complement each other because clustering can be used as a preprocessing step before applying supervised predictive models. K-Means, for instance, can be employed to segment properties with similar characteristics before applying a regression model or neural network. Moreover, hybrid methods like PSO-Bagging-ANNs (Particle Swarm Optimization + Ensemble Learning) combine particle swarm optimization with an ensemble of neural networks to improve prediction accuracy [4]. This demonstrates that combining techniques can improve prediction effectiveness by leveraging both segmentation and supervised learning for better data analysis.

RQ3: How can ML algorithms be tailored to enhance both clustering and predictive performance? The adaptation of ML algorithms can improve both clustering and predictive performance by adjusting hyperparameters and selecting appropriate techniques. Regularization methods like LASSO, RIDGE, and ElasticNet were applied in 50%, 40% and 20%, respectively, of studies, highlighting their role in variable selection and reducing model complexity, helping to mitigate overfitting and enhance interpretability.

In predictive modeling, optimization strategies such as PSO-Bagging-ANNs (Particle Swarm Optimization + Ensemble Learning) combine Particle Swarm Optimization with an ensemble of Neural Networks to improve prediction accuracy [4]. Similarly, Genetic Algorithms (GA) are optimization techniques inspired by natural selection, often used to fine-tune parameters in ML models [6]. These methods help enhance model performance by optimizing hyperparameters and improving learning efficiency.

For clustering, approaches like SCMCA focused on geographic clustering to reveal spatial patterns [9]. These strategies collectively enable models to better fit the data and improve generalization capabilities.

RQ4: What are the key challenges in selecting and optimizing ML algorithms for clustering and prediction? Selecting and optimizing ML algorithms for real estate analysis involves several intertwined challenges related to the complexity of the data, interpretability of models, and data quality. Real estate datasets often include a mixture of structured variables (such as price, area, or location) alongside unstructured inputs like textual descriptions, images, and user reviews, which add layers of complexity and require advanced techniques to analyze effectively [1, 4]. Additionally, some advanced ML models, while accurate, are difficult to interpret, posing a barrier to their practical adoption [4]. The evaluation of these predictive models relies on various performance metrics, with around 60% of studies favoring MAPE as the primary measure of accuracy. To overcome these challenges, methods such as sentiment analysis, Natural Language Processing

(NLP), and computer vision have been applied to extract and integrate richer information from diverse data types [4]. This shows that successful model optimization depends not only on choosing appropriate algorithms but also on tailoring them to the unique characteristics of the real estate data.

Building on these general challenges, several specific difficulties emerge in real estate market trend analysis and prediction, ranging from managing diverse and unstructured data to dealing with data availability, quality, and the inherent limitations of advanced predictive models. Furthermore, combining different analytical methods can add complexity, requiring careful handling. The main challenges and possible strategies to address them are outlined below:

1. Complexity of Data and Unstructured Variables

Real estate market analysis faces significant complexity due to the coexistence of structured data, such as price, area, or location, and unstructured inputs like textual descriptions, images, and user reviews [1]. Many critical variables, such as neighborhood perception or aesthetic features, are qualitative and difficult to quantify, often escaping traditional models [3]. NLP can help extract relevant information from inconsistent listing texts, while computer vision enables the evaluation of property condition through images [1, 3]. By combining numerical, textual, and visual data within multimodal models, predictive performance can be significantly enhanced [4], supporting more accurate valuations and tailored property recommendations.

2. Data Availability and Quality

The lack of a centralized infrastructure leads to fragmented and inconsistent data across real estate platforms, public records, and agencies [9]. Many datasets contain missing, outdated, or poorly recorded information, making accurate prediction difficult. Techniques like data imputation and integration platforms help address missing values and standardize disparate sources [9]. Furthermore, collaboration between public and private stakeholders could improve data reliability and ensure up-to-date and comprehensive datasets, especially when shared standards are adopted for information collection and categorization. Privacy regulations restrict direct access to individual transaction data, requiring the use of aggregated or complementary data sources to maintain data comprehensiveness and reliability [5].

3. Low Interpretability of Advanced Models

Despite their accuracy, advanced models such as deep neural networks, Random Forest, and XGBoost are often difficult to interpret [1, 2]. This limits their usability in practice, as real estate professionals need to understand the reasoning behind model predictions. To improve transparency, these models can be combined with more interpretable methods, such as logistic regression, or supported by Explainable AI (XAI) techniques [4]. Tools like SHAP and LIME allow for the identification of which variables influence specific predictions, providing clarity to end users [1].

4. Sensitivity to External Economic and Political Changes

The real estate market is heavily influenced by regional and socioeconomic factors such as income, demographics, and urban-rural differences. These variables reflect economic and social changes that models relying solely on historical data struggle to predict. Incorporating regional indicators improves model adaptability to external variations and enhances prediction accuracy [5].

5. Challenges in Integrating Clustering and Predictive Models

Combining clustering algorithms (like K-Means or DBSCAN) with predictive models presents computational challenges and risks compromising performance if parameters are poorly set [9]. For example, choosing the wrong number of clusters may result in data overgeneralization and reduced accuracy. Automated feature selection could help simplify model inputs, focusing only on the most relevant variables [1]. A promising solution lies in semi-supervised models, which combine unsupervised clustering with supervised learning, leveraging the strengths of both techniques for improved predictive performance [1].

6 Conclusion

This Literature review analyzed the use of clustering and predictive models in real estate, demonstrating their effectiveness in trend prediction and property segmentation. Combining clustering algorithms like K-Means, DBSCAN, and Hierarchical Clustering with predictive models such as Linear Regression, Random Forest, and Neural Networks enhanced prediction accuracy and categorization [1, 2, 3, 4]. Challenges included data complexity, unstructured variables, data quality, and interpretability of advanced ML models [1, 3, 4, 5, 9]. Emerging techniques like sentiment analysis, NLP, and computer vision could address these issues for deeper insights [1, 3, 4]. Future directions include integrating

multimodal models, real-time data systems, and AI-based early warning systems, which could transform market analysis and provide strategic support to stakeholders [1, 2, 4]. Overall, the synergy of clustering and predictive modeling marks a significant advance in real estate analysis, enabling more informed decisions and effective investment strategies.

This study has some limitations that should be acknowledged. The search string used, while precise, may have excluded relevant studies, for not using the root of some words instead of the words. This could have resulted in a smaller sample of articles than potentially available. Future research could benefit from broader search terms and more string variations to ensure a more comprehensive coverage of the existing literature on machine learning applications in real estate.

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